

IFIH1 (aka MDA5)

(Interferon induced with helicase C domain 1)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID	64135 / Q9BYX4
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
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Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
Document version	1.0
Document version date	November 2025
Citation	10.5281/zenodo.17645183
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SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a debilitating brain disorder that affects more than 7 million Americans aged 65 and older [1] and has no known effective treatment to date. The past two decades of AD drug discovery efforts have focused on a few therapeutic hypotheses with little success in developing game-changing therapies for human use. To this end, the National Institute on Aging has launched the TREAT-AD initiative (TaRget Enablement to Accelerate Therapy Development for AD), which aims to improve the robustness of and diversify the portfolio of AD drug targets by accelerating the characterization and experimental validation of next-generation therapeutic targets. Among others, the IFIH1 helicase was nominated by the consortium to study its potential role in AD progression (<https://agora.adknowledgeportal.org/genes>). IFIH1 (encoding the MDA5 protein) is a member of the DExH-box family of helicases, specifically the RIG-1-like receptor subfamily, that utilizes a dynamic response of filament aggregation and dissociation from dsRNA, mediated in part by ATP hydrolysis, for the recognition and immune targeting of viral RNA [2,3]. As part of TREAT-AD, we aim to generate Target Enabling Packages (TEPs), including validation antibodies, purified proteins, and high-throughput biochemical activity assays to enable the discovery of small molecule chemical probes to enable evaluation of the role of IFIH1 in AD progression and whether its inhibition has therapeutic potential for the treatment of AD.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

IFIH1 is a member of the RIG-1-like receptor subfamily of helicases, alongside RIG-1 and DHX58. IFIH1, encoding the MDA5 protein, responds to viral RNA, namely dsRNA, and plays a role in the innate immune response leveraged in response to these nucleic acids. After binding to viral RNA, MDA5 activates downstream signaling pathways, triggering the production of type I interferon and additional inflammatory cytokines [4]. The interaction between MDA5 and RNA is reported to be regulated by another RIG-1-like receptor family helicase, DHX58 (gene encoding the LGP2 protein) [5,6]. MDA5 does not unwind dsRNA. Instead, it forms oligomeric filaments along the dsRNA, potentially promoting a conformational change favoring interactions with key anti-viral signaling proteins [2,3,7]. The role that IFIH1/MDA5 plays in the innate immune response may be relevant to the viral hypothesis of AD, where exposure to certain types of infections may be associated with disease pathogenesis [8]. Indeed, it has been found that amyloid beta fibrils that contain nucleic acids (such as dsRNA) can trigger a type I interferon response that is particularly detrimental to neurons and synapses [9]. As MDA5 represents a key signaling bridge between presence of

nucleic acids and the triggering of this immune response, the inhibition of IFIH1/MDA5 could have beneficial effects in dampening the hyper-neuroinflammatory state characteristic of AD.

Structurally, MDA5 consists of two N-terminal CARD domains, a helicase domain, and a carboxy-terminal domain (CTD). The interaction of CARD1 and CARD2 with mitochondrial antiviral-signaling protein (MAV), which is anchored in the mitochondria, leads to downstream activation of interferon regulatory factors (IRF3 and IRF7) and transcription factors (NF- κ B) that induce expression of various genes [10].

Mutations in IFIH1/MDA5 are linked to various autoimmune diseases, including Aicardi-Goutières syndrome, systemic lupus erythematosus [11], Singleton-Merten syndrome, spastic-dystonic syndrome, and neuroregression [12]. An MDA5 variant, M854K, can also perturb the interaction between MDA5 and dsRNA, resulting in activation of interferon signaling without the need for exogenous RNA [12].

BIOINFORMATIC ANALYSIS

Target Source & Hypothesis

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [13]. Gene set enrichment analysis of all scored genes highlights the "innate immune response" Gene Ontology (GO) term as one of the most significantly enriched among genes with the highest Target Risk Score. This GO term was also identified through analysis of transcriptomic and proteomic pseudotime states [14] as being among the processes for which there is evidence of differential expression in early states of disease progression. Among the leading edge (i.e. top-scoring) genes in the "innate immune response" GO term were a set of RNA helicase proteins including IFIH1, DHX58, and DDX1. Network pathway modeling identified these as central nodes within the network related to innate immune response, and analysis of patient pseudotime indicates the expression of these genes changes in early disease pseudo-states. These targets were nominated within a hypothesis that over-activation of the innate immune response triggers aberrant cytokine signaling and excessive phagocytosis of synapses and neurons, leading to neurodegenerative pathogenesis in AD.

IFIH1 has a TREAT-AD Target Risk Score of 2.96 out of 5 (rank #5254, 79th percentile) (**Fig. 1A**). The individual score components include 1.41 of 3 (51.6th percentile) for genetics (**Fig. 1B**), and 1.55 out of 2 (83.1st percentile) for genomics (**Fig. 1C**). The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of the IFIH1 RNA is significantly higher in brains from patients with AD, while protein was not detected.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD) (sea-ad.org, [15]). The expression of IFIH1 was averaged across cells within a supertype from each donor. The locally weighted mean expression (LOWESS) of superotypes within each subclass is then plotted across the range of continuous donor pseudo-progression, which orders subjects based on a learned model of neuropathological burden. IFIH1 is expressed primarily in Endothelial and Microglia cell types from the SEA-AD dataset (**Fig. 1D**). IFIH1 expression is stable within cell types subclasses across donor pseudo-progression.

Figure 1. (A) TREAT-AD Target Risk Score, **(B)** component genetic risk score and **(C)** multi-omic risk score for IFIH1. The lines within the score and component score violin plots show the 50th and 90th percentile scores. **(D)** IFIH1 cell-type expression data from SEA-AD. Cell type expression plots show the locally weighted mean expression of cell supertypes from each donor within each subclass along donor pseudo-progression.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains) [13]. These biodomains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biodomains via GO term annotations. IFIH1 is annotated to GO terms from 4 biodomain(s), primarily to terms from the Immune Response, RNA Spliceosome, and Metal Binding and Homeostasis domain(s) (**Fig. 2A**).

The CRISPRbrain resource (crisprbrain.org, [16]) is a data commons for functional genomics datasets from differentiated human iPSC derived cell types. The resource reports phenotype results following CRISPR screens of gene activation (CRISPRa), inhibition (CRISPRi), or gene knockout (CRISPRn), in iPSC derived brain-relevant cell types. Following the screens, genes are identified as either positive or negative hits, meaning perturbation leads to a significant and reproducible increase or decrease in the measured phenotype, respectively, or a non-hit if the perturbation does not significantly impact the phenotype. IFIH1 is not a hit in any assay (**Fig. 2B**).

Figure 2. (A) IFIH1 TREAT-AD biological domain annotations and **(B)** phenotypes from CRISPR screens in iPSC derived cell types from the CRISPRbrain resource.

VALIDATED ANTIBODIES AND KNOCKOUT CELL LINES

YCharOS Antibody Characterization

Understanding the etiology of Alzheimer’s disease (AD) requires a comprehensive molecular and biological investigation of the approximately 184 genes and corresponding proteins linked to AD risk. However, research efforts remain heavily skewed: just three genes—APP, APOE, and MAPT (tau)—account for 49% of all AD-related publications indexed on PubMed. This imbalance underscores the urgent need to expand the focus to include the broader landscape of AD-associated proteins.

A key barrier to this expansion is the limited availability of selective and renewable antibodies for many of these understudied proteins. The TREAT-AD program aims to address this gap by identifying or developing high-quality research tools for less-characterized AD-associated proteins, enabling rigorous hypothesis testing [17].

The Antibody Characterization through Open Science (YCharOS) initiative, led from McGill University, is a global, public-good effort uniting academic researchers, funding agencies, 13 leading antibody manufacturers, and two knockout cell line providers. Using industry-endorsed protocols [18], YCharOS systematically evaluates antibody performance with the goal of identifying one or more high-quality renewable antibodies (e.g., monoclonal or recombinant) per human protein target. Antibodies are tested side-by-side in immunoblot (western blot), immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using isogenic knockout cell lines as controls. All results are shared openly and rapidly via the AD Knowledge Portal (<https://adknowledgeportal.synapse.org/>) and in the Zenodo YCharOS community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/treatad/>).

Here, nine IFIH1/MDA5 antibodies—sourced from seven companies and spanning recombinant, monoclonal, and polyclonal formats—were evaluated using an siRNA targeting IFIH1. While specific renewable antibodies suitable for immunoblot and immunoprecipitation were identified, none of the antibodies showed specificity in immunofluorescence under the conditions tested. This characterization report provides researchers with data-driven guidance to select the most appropriate antibodies for studying IFIH1, and is available on Zenodo. Complete report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17475726> [19]

HISTOLOGY

MDA5 localization in AD and control forebrain tissue

MDK protein expression and localization were detected by immunohistochemistry using anti-MDA5 antibodies MA5-55914 from Invitrogen (**Fig. 3**) and 66770-1 from ProteinTech (data not shown) in AD (right) and control (left) human forebrain tissue. Representative images using MA5-55914 antibody are demonstrated in the figure below. Cytoplasmic MDA5 immunoreactivity (ir) is detected in all cell types. No difference in ir is noted between the control and AD brain tissue samples. In addition, MDA5-ir was not noted in plaques or tangle-like structures in AD brain sections. Similar MDA5-ir was detected with both antibodies.

Figure 3. Immunohistochemistry of MDA5 in human forebrain tissue. Paraffin embedded brain sections from the frontal cortex were processed for immunocytochemistry from control (“CONT”) and AD patient (“AD”) brains. Representative images demonstrate MDA5-immunoreactivity (ir) with Invitrogen antibody MA5-55914 and counter-stained with cresyl-violet. Please note the cytoplasmic MDA5-ir in all cell types in the brain including pyramidal neurons with large and glial cells with small nuclei. Scale bar = 50µm.

See **Additional information (section 1)** for more details.

PROTEIN CONSTRUCTS AND EXPRESSION METHODS

Protein Purified

1. FL-MDA5: Full-length Biotinylated & His-tagged MDA5: Full-length construct (aa1-1025) of human MDA5. Contains an N-terminal AviTag biotinylation signal and C-terminal His6 tag. Protein produced in sf9 insect cells. Used in ATPase assay.
2. Δ CARD-MDA5: CARD domain-truncated Biotinylated & His-tagged MDA5: Truncated construct (aa306-1025) of human MDA5. Contains an N-terminal AviTag biotinylation signal and C-terminal His6 tag. Protein produced in sf9 insect cells. Used in ATPase assay, SPR, FP.
3. Δ CARD/loop-MDA5: CARD domain-and-loop-truncated His-tagged MDA5: Truncated construct (aa306-644, 663-1017) of human MDA5. N-terminal His tag removed. Used for crystallography trials.
4. S-MDA5: CARD domain-/ C-terminus domain-/ and loop-truncated His-tagged MDA5: Truncated construct (aa306-644, 663-890) of human MDA5. N-terminal His tag removed. Used for crystallography trials.

See **Additional information (section 2)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

BIOCHEMICAL ASSAYS

ATPase Activity Assay

Helicases classically utilize the energy derived from ATP hydrolysis for duplex RNA unwinding. MDA5, however, does not unwind dsRNA, and instead utilizes ATP hydrolysis to form filaments, translocate, and/ or dissociate from viral RNA [2,3,7]. Here, we developed a high-throughput ATPase activity assay to screen for compounds that inhibit the ATPase activity of MDA5 (**Fig. 4A, B**) [20]. The assay uses a 24-mer dsRNA (GGGACGUCAUGCGCAUGACGUCCC) from IDT (Integrated DNA Technologies, USA) as a substrate and measures the level of leftover ATP in each reaction using the Kinase-Glo reagent (Promega, Cat# V6712; Promega, Madison, WI, USA). The reaction mixtures contained 4 μ M ATP and 20 nM of 24-mer dsRNA in 20 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.5, 0.01% Tween 20, 1 mM MgCl₂, and 2 mM DTT), with a final volume of 15 μ L per well. The reactions were initiated by adding MDA5 at a final concentration of 20 nM. The reaction mixtures were incubated for 30–60 min and then quenched by adding 15 μ L of luciferase reagent mix to each well. Subsequently, 25 μ L of the mixture from each well was transferred to a 384-well white detection plate and incubated for an additional 15 min before measuring luminescence signals using a BioTek Synergy 4 plate reader, as relative light units (RLU). The data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel and GraphPad Prism 8. We also determined the Z'-factor for the MDA5 ATPase assay, showing that this assay is amenable for high-throughput screening (**Fig. 4C**). The ATPase activity of several MDA5 constructs of different length were also tested utilizing this approach (**Fig. 5**). This demonstrates that the C-terminus domain (aa891-1025) is crucial for the ATPase activity of MDA5, as it is involved in nucleic acid binding. The difference in activity between the full-length and the Δ CARD can be attributed to the stability of the purified protein in solution.

Figure 4. MDA5 ATPase activity assay for compound screening. (A) Schematic overview of ATPase activity assay. (B) Km determinations for 24-mer RNA with MDA5. The addition of 24mer-RNA promotes MDA5 ATPase activity in a concentration dependent manner. (C) Z'-factor determination for MDA5. The activity RLU without MDA5 (●) and with MDA5 (■) wells. Z'-factor calculated as previously described [21].

Figure 5. ATPase activity of different lengths of MDA5. ΔCARD-MDA5 (●), full-length (■) and S-MDA5 (▲) [20].

Fluorescence Polarization (FP) assay

MDA5 binds to dsRNA *in vitro*. To identify ligands that can disrupt the nucleic acid binding ability of MDA5, we developed a FP displacement assay for compound screening. Assays were performed in a final volume of 20 μ L in black flat bottom 384-well polypropylene microplates (Greiner ref. no. 784209) and measured on a Synergy H1 (BioTek) plate reader using 485/20 nm excitation and 528/20 nm emission filters. Buffer condition: 20 mM HEPES, pH 7.5, 150 mM NaCl, 0.01% Triton X-100, 1mM TCEP and 2mM $MgCl_2$.

To first determine the binding between MDA5 and a designed 12mer-RNA (56-FAM-AGGGCCGCGGAU) from IDT (Integrated DNA Technologies, USA), Δ CARD-MDA5 was titrated from 40 to 0 μ M to obtain the equilibrium dissociation constant (K_d) of 1.3 μ M (Fig. 6A). A competitive nucleic acid displacement assay was then conducted with the unlabeled counterpart using a protein concentration at 60% saturation (2 μ M). MDA5 was first incubated with unlabeled 12mer-dsRNA for 1 hr, followed by 30 min with the tracer nucleic acid at room temperature for 30 min before the FP signal was measured. The resulting dose–response curve was fitted to a four-parameter sigmoidal model by using GraphPad Prism to obtain the K displacement (K_{disp}) of 5.8 μ M (Fig. 6B).

Figure 6. Binding and displacement parameter determination for 12mer-RNA and MDA5. (A) Binding saturation curve and (B) competitive FAM-12merRNA displacement by the unlabelled 12merRNA. Errors are represented as \pm SE (n=3).

CELL-BASED ASSAYS

Knockdown in iPSC neurons

shRNA targeting IFIH1 was used to knockdown IFIH1 expression in iPSC-derived neurons from the human iPS lines WTC11 (APOE3/3) and CVi (APOE 3/4). The knockdown was more than 75% effective in both lines (**Fig. 8A**). Reduction of IFIH1 expression did not result in significantly increased cytotoxicity in the CVi line but demonstrated slight cytotoxicity in the WTC11 line (**Fig. 8B**). Secreted A β 38, A β 40, and A β 42 (**Fig. 8C-E**) decreased the conditioned media with IFIH1 knockdown in both lines, but the A β 42/A β 40 ratio did not change (**Fig. 8F**). Total tau and tau phosphorylated at Thr231 (pTau) levels (**Fig. 8G and H**) were decreased in the CVi line following IFIH1 knockdown but only pTau was decreased in the WTC11 neurons. The pTau/totalTau ratio (**Fig. 8I**) decreased with IFIH1 knockdown in the CVi line but remained unchanged in the WTC11 line.

Figure 8. Knockdown in iPSC neurons. (A) Knockdown of IFIH1 in CVi- and WTC11-derived neurons confirmed by qPCR in cell lysates as compared to cells transduced with scrambled shRNA as a negative control (1 biological replicate x 3 technical replicates with two primer sets). (B) Cytotoxicity as measured by LDH production and detected by the Promega LDH-Glo Cytotoxicity Assay in both lines following IFIH1 knockdown (n=2 biological replicates x 2 technical replicates). (C-F) Secreted A β 38, A β 40, A β 42, and A β 42/A β 40 ratio in conditioned media from CVi (left) and WTC11 (right) derived neurons (n=2 biological replicates x 2 technical replicates). (G-I) Total Tau, pTau, and pTau/totalTau ratio in CVi (left) and WTC11 (right) cell lysates (n=2 biological replicates x 2 technical replicates). *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001, ns= p>0.05.

See **Additional information (section 3)** for more details.

CONCLUSION

IFIH1 is a member of the DEXH-box family of helicases, specifically the RIG-1-like receptor subfamily, which was selected as an AD target based on its AD Target Risk Score formulated using genetics and genomics data. IFIH1 was annotated with TREAT-AD-defined GO biodomains for Immune Response, RNA Splicesome, and Metal Binding and Homeostasis. RNA levels for IFIH1 are higher in the brains of patients with AD, and the role of IFIH1 in the innate immune response, with activation resulting in innate immune signaling and the potential downstream phagocytosis of synapses and neurons, makes this an attractive target for AD.

Firstly, to enable the study of IFIH1 (and the protein it encodes, MDA5) in cells, antibodies were validated using siRNA-mediated knock-down (KD) in cells, and renewable antibodies suitable for immunoblot and

immunoprecipitation were identified. However, none of the tested antibodies showed specificity when used in immunofluorescence experiments. Immunohistochemistry using one of the validated antibodies in human brain tissue from people with AD and controls confirmed the utility of the antibody for this additional application. To determine the effect of IFIH1 reduction on AD pathology, IFIH1 was knocked down with shRNA in CVi and WTC11-derived neurons. This resulted in decreased A β 38, A β 40, and A β 42 in the secreted iPSC media from both lines, but no change in the A β 42/A β 40 ratio was observed. Furthermore, the p-Tau/total-Tau ratio was only decreased in CVi with IFIH1 KD.

For the enablement of biochemical assays, as well as co-crystallography, protein was generated for FL-MDA5, Δ CARD-MDA5, Δ CARD/loop-MDA5, and S-MDA5 constructs. A biochemical ATPase assay was developed in a high-throughput format utilizing both FL-MDA5 and Δ CARD-MDA5 in combination with 24-mer dsRNA and ATP to enable screening for small molecule ATPase inhibitors. To determine the ability of compounds to displace dsRNA from MDA5, an FP assay was established with Δ CARD-MDA5 and FAM 12mer-RNA. These reagents and assays will facilitate the discovery of chemical probes that could be used to further interrogate the role of helicase IFIH1/MDA5 in the context of AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

1. Immunohistochemistry in human brain tissue

Methods are described in full in the original publication of data [22]. In brief, human forebrain 8- μ m-thick sections were obtained from 3 control and 3 AD diagnosed cases from the Emory CND Neuropathology and Histology Core and processed for immunohistochemistry by the same core. Sections were deparaffinized and processed for immunohistochemical labeling on a ThermoFisher autostainer. Sections were processed for antigen retrieval if needed, blocked with normal serum. MDA5 was detected with primary anti-MDA5 antibodies MA5-55914 from Invitrogen (mouse, 1:1000) and 66770-1 from ProteinTech (mouse, 1:1000) and secondary antibody biotinylated goat anti-rabbit 111-065-003 (Jackson ImmunoResearch Laboratories) at 1:200. Sections were then exposed to avidin-biotin complex (Vector ABC Elite Kit) and developed with diaminobenzidine. Images were captured with an Aperio scanner and processed using Adobe Photoshop software.

2. Protein expression constructs and protein purification

All relevant plasmids are available on Addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

1. Full length Biotinylated & His-tagged MDA5

Sample ID	PBC037-B09
Purpose	ATPase assay
Vector	pFBD-BirA
AA start to end	1-1025
N-terminal tag	MSGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSG
C-terminal tag	GGSGHHHHHH
Expected Mass (Da)	120321.89
Protein sequence	MSGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSGMSNGYSTDENFRYLISCFRARVKMYIQVEPVLDTFLP AEVKEQIQRTVATSGNMQAVELLSTLEKGVVHLGWTRFVEALRRTGSPLAARYMNP DLPSPSFENAHDEYLQLLNLLQPTLVDKLLVRDVLDKCMEELLTIEDRNRIAAENNGNESGV RELLKRIVQKENWFS AFLNVL RQTGNNELVQELTGSDCSESNAEIENLSQVDGPQVEEQLLST TVQPNLEKEVWGMENNSSESSFADSSVSESDTSLAEGSVSCLDESLGHNSNMGSDSGTMG SDSDEENVAARASPEPELQLRPYQMEVAQPALEGKNIICLPTGSGKTRVAVYIAKDHLDKKKK ASEPGKVIVLVNKVLLVEQLFRKEFQPFLLKRWYRVIGLSGDTQLKISFPEVVKSCDIISTAQILEN SLLNLENGEDAGVQLSDFSLIIDECHHTNKEAVYNNIMRHYLMQKLKNNRLKKNKPIPLP QILGLTASPGVGGATKQAKAEHILKLCANLDAFTIKTVKENLDQLKNQIQEPCKKFAIADATR EDPFKEKLEIMTRIQTTCMQSPMSDFGTQPYEQWAIQMEKKAKEG NRKERVCAEHLRKY NEALQINDTIRMIDAYTHLETFYNEEKDKKFAVIEDDSDEGGDDEYCDGDEDEDDLKPLKLD ETDRFLMTLFFENKMLKRLAENPEYENEKLTCLRNTIMEQYTRTEESARGIIFTKTRQSAYALS QWITENEKFAEVGVKAHHLIGAGHSSEFKPMTQNEQKEVISKFRGTGKINLIATTVAEEGLDIK ECNIVIRYGLVTNEIAMVQARGRARADESTYVLVAHSGSGVIERETVNDFREKMMYKAIHCV QNMKPEEYAHKILELQMQSIMEKKMKT KRNI AKHYKNNPSLITFLCKNC SVLACSGEDIHVIE KMHHVNMTPFEKELYIVRENKTLQKKCADYQINGEICKCGQAWGTMMMVHKGLDLPCLKIR NFVVVFKNNSTKKQYKKVWELPITFPNLDYSECCLFSDEDDGGSGHHHHHH

Purified protein (PBC037B09)	
IMAC, TALON (step 1):	NA
SEC (step 2):	<p>MDA5A_FL_Sf9_AviTag PBC037B09 GF profile Mar. 14/2022</p>

Source 30Q (step 3):	
Intact mass deconvolution (Da):	NA
Protein yield:	0.085 mg/L culture
Expression and purification protocol	<p>The wild-type gene of MDA5A-FL (aa1-1025) was PCR amplified and subcloned into pFBD-BirA vector. Proteins were expressed in Sf9 insect cells using biotin-supplemented media and harvested 72-96 h post-infection following a previously reported protocol [23]. Harvested cells were resuspended in 20 mM Tris-HCL, pH 7.5, 500 mM NaCl and 5% glycerol, 1X protease inhibitor cocktail (100 X protease inhibitor stock in 70% ethanol (0.25 mg/mL Aprotinin, 0.25 mg/mL Leupeptin, 0.25 mg/mL Pepstatin A and 0.25 mg/mL E-64). The cells were lysed chemically with 0.5% NP40 and benzonase (in-house), followed by sonication at frequency of 7.0 (5" on/7" off) for 2 min (Sonicator 3000, Misoni). The crude extract was clarified by high-speed centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 60 min at 10 °C by Beckman Coulter centrifuge. The clarified lysate was incubated with pre-equilibrated TALON affinity resin (Clontech) for 45 min at 4 °C. The lysate was then passed through an open column, and washed twice and eluted by 20 mM Tris-HCL pH 7.5, 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, containing 0mM, 5mM and 250mM imidazole, respectively. The eluted protein was supplemented with 1mM TCEP and further purified by size-exclusion chromatography on a Superdex200 26/60 column using an ÄKTA FPLC system (GE Healthcare, Little Chalfont, UK). with a running buffer containing 20 mM Tris-HCL pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl. The protein was further purified by anion exchange chromatography using a Source 30Q column pre-equilibrated with 20 mM Tris-HCL pH 7.5 and eluted with 20 mM Tris-HCL pH 7.5 at a concentration gradient of 1 M NaCl. The protein was supplemented with 2mM TCEP and 1,2-propanediol.</p>

2. CARD domain-truncated Biotinylated & His-tagged MDA5

Sample ID	PBC037-C05
Purpose	ATPase assay, SPR, FP
Vector	pFBD-BirA
AA start to end	306-1025

N-terminal tag	MSGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSG
C-terminal tag	GGSGHHHHHH
Expected Mass (Da)	86373.31
Protein sequence	MSGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSGLQLRPYQMEVAQPALEGKNIICLPTGSGKTRVAVYIAK DHLDKKKKASEPGKVIVLVNKKVLLVEQLFRKEFQPFLLKKWYRVIGLSGDTQLKISFPEVVKSCDII ISTAQILENSLLNLENGEDAGVQLSDFSLIIDECHHTNKEAVYNNIMRHYLMQKLNKNNRLKKE NKPVIPLPQILGLTASPGVGGATKQAKAEHILKLCANLDAFTIKTVKENLDQLKNQIQEPCKKF AIADATREDPFKEKLEIMTRIQTTCQMSDFGTQPYEQWAIQMEKKAKEGNRKERVC AEHLRKYNEALQINDTIRMIDAYTHLETFYNEEKDKKFAVIEDDSDEGGDDEYCDGDEDEDL KKPLKLDLDRFLMTLFFENKMLKRLAENPEYENEKLTCLRNTIMEQYTRTEESARGIIFTKTR QSAYALSQWITENEKFAEVGVKAHHLIGAGHSSEFKPMTQNEQKEVSKFRTGKINLLIATTVA EEGLDIKECNIVIRYGLVTNEIAMVQARGRARADESTYVLVAHSGSGVIERETVNDFREKMMY KAIHCVQNMKPEEYAHKILELQMQSIMEKKMKTNRNIAKHYNPNSLITFLCKNCSVLACSGE DIHVIEKMHVNMTPFEKELYIVRENKTLQKKCADYQINGEIIICKGQAWGTMMVHKGLDL PCLKIRNFVVFKNNSTKKQYKKWVLELPITFPNLDYSECCLFSDDEDGGSGHHHHHH

Purified protein (PBC037C05)	
IMAC, TALON (step 1):	
SEC (step 2):	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div> <p>GF profile.</p> <p>Collected: D11 to E11</p> </div> <div> <p>MDA5A PBC37C5 2023-09-19 GF S200 26-600 Position5 002 001</p> </div> </div>

Intact mass deconvolution (Da):	<p>86587</p>
Protein yield:	4.6 mg/L culture
Expression and purification protocol	<p>The wild-type gene of MDA5A (aa306-1025) was PCR amplified and subcloned into the pFBD-BirA vector. Proteins were expressed in Sf9 insect cells using biotin-supplemented media and harvested 72-96 h post-infection following a previously reported protocol [23]. Harvested cells were resuspended in 20 mM Hepes, pH 7.5, 500 mM NaCl, 5 mM imidazole and 5% glycerol, 1X protease inhibitor cocktail (100 X protease inhibitor stock in 70% ethanol (0.25 mg/mL Aprotinin, 0.25 mg/mL Leupeptin, 0.25 mg/mL Pepstatin A and 0.25 mg/mL E-64). The cells were lysed chemically with 0.5% NP40 and benzonase (in-house), followed by sonication at frequency of 7.0 (5" on/7" off) for 2 min (Sonicator 3000, Misoni). The crude extract was clarified by high-speed centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 60 min at 10 °C by Beckman Coulter centrifuge. The clarified lysate was passed through an open column containing equilibrated Ni-NTA resins. The column was first washed with 20 mM Hepes, pH 7.5, 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, and 5 mM imidazole. A second wash with the same buffer containing 1 M NaCl and 5 mM imidazole was performed to remove bound nucleic acids. A third wash with 30 mM imidazole and 500 mM NaCl was applied, and the target protein was finally eluted with 250 mM imidazole in the same buffer. The eluted protein was supplemented with 1mM TCEP and further purified by size-exclusion chromatography on a Superdex200 26/60 column using an ÄKTA Pure (Cytiva) system with a running buffer containing 20 mM Hepes, pH 7.5, 300 mM NaCl, 1 mM TCEP.</p>

3. CARD domain-and-loop-truncated MDA5

Sample ID	PBC037-B11
Purpose	Crystal trials
Vector	pFBOH-MHL
AA start to end	306-1017
N-terminal tag	MHHHHHSSGRENLYFQG
C-terminal tag	NA
Expected Mass (Da)	82108.18/ 79971.88 after His6 cleavage

Protein sequence	MHHHHHHSSGRENLYFQGLQLRPYQMEVAQPALEGKNIICLPTGSGKTRVAVYIAKDHLDK KKKASEPGKVIVLVNKKVLLVEQLFRKEFQPFLLKWWYRVIGLSGDTQLKISFPEVVKSCDIIISTAQI LENSLLNLENGEDAGVQLSDFSLIIDECHHTNKEAVYNNIMRHVLMQKLNKNNRLKKNKPVIP LPQILGLTASPGVGGATKQAKAEHILKLCANLDAFTIKTVKENLDQLKNQIQEPCKKFAIADA TREDPFKEKLEIMTRIQTTCQMSPMSDFGTQPYEQWAIQMEKKAKEGNRKERVCAEHLR KYNEALQINDTIRMIDAYTHLETIFYNEEKDKKFAVIEDD_LKKPLKLDLDRFLMTLFFENKMK LKRLAENPEYENEKLTCLRNTIMEQYTRTEESARGIIFTKTRQSAYALSQWITENEKFAEVGVKA HHLIGAGHSSEFKPMTQNEQKEVISKFRGTGINLLIATTVAEEGLDIKECNIVIRYGLVTNEIAM VQARGRARADESTYVLVAHSGSGVIERETVNDFREKMMYKAIHCVQNMKPEEYAHKILELQ MQSIMEKKMKTKRNIAKHYKNNPSLITFLCKNCSVLACSGEDIHVIEKMHHVNMTPFEKELYI VRENKTLQKKCADYQINGEIIICKCGQAWGTMMVHKGLDLPCLKIRNFVVVFKNNSTKKQYK KWVELPITFPNLDYSE
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Purified protein (PBC037B11)	
IMAC, TALON (step 1):	<p>M ft w1 w2 e1 e2 e3 e4 pooled Collected e1-4</p>
SEC (step 2):	<p>M a7 b4 b9 c6 c11 d1 d6 e2 e9 e12 f3 f9 g2 g9 Collected D1-E12</p> <p>20250815_MDA5_PBC037B11_S200_001</p>
TEV cleavage & Source 30S (step 3):	<p>un cut M e10 f12 g11 h2 h4 h8 h12 a2 a3 a5 a11 b10 Collected h2- a5</p> <p>20250816_MDA5_PBC037B11_001</p>

Reverse TALON (step 4):	<p>a M ft w1 w2 w3 e b protein diluted to 1 mg/ml, 5mM imidazole + 100 ul Talon beads added a: before Ft: flow through (final fraction) W1: 5mM imi W2: 25mM W3: 50mM e: 250mM b: bead</p>
Intact mass deconvolution (Da):	NA
Protein yield:	1.3 mg/L culture
Expression and purification protocol	<p>The wild-type gene of MDA5A (aa306-644, 663-1017) was PCR amplified and subcloned into the pFBD-MHL vector. Proteins were expressed in Sf9 insect cells and harvested 72-96 h post-infection following a previously reported protocol [23]. Harvested cells were resuspended in 20 mM Hepes, pH 7.4, 500 mM NaCl, 5 mM imidazole and 5% glycerol, 1X protease inhibitor cocktail (100 X protease inhibitor stock in 70% ethanol (0.25 mg/mL Aprotinin, 0.25 mg/mL Leupeptin, 0.25 mg/mL Pepstatin A and 0.25 mg/mL E-64). The cells were lysed chemically with 0.5% NP40 and benzonase (in-house), followed by sonication at frequency of 7.0 (5" on/7" off) for 2 min (Sonicator 3000, Misoni). The crude extract was clarified by high-speed centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 60 min at 10 °C by Beckman Coulter centrifuge. The clarified lysate was incubated with pre-equilibrated TALON affinity resin (Clontech) for 45 min at 4 °C. The lysate was then passed through an open column, and washed twice and eluted by 20 mM Hepes pH 7.4, 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, containing 0mM, 5mM and 250mM imidazole, respectively. The eluted protein was supplemented with 1mM TCEP and further purified by size-exclusion chromatography on a Superdex200 26/60 column using an ÄKTA Pure (Cytiva) system with a running buffer containing 20 mM Hepes, pH 7.5, 250 mM NaCl, 1 mM TCEP. Proteins were pooled and incubated overnight at 4 °C with tobacco etch virus protease (TEV) to cleave the His6 tag. The protein was further purified by cation exchange chromatography using a Source 30S column pre-equilibrated with 20 mM Hepes, pH 7.4 and eluted with 20 mM Hepes, pH 7.4 at a concentration gradient of 1 M NaCl. The protein was finally incubated with 100 ul of TALON beads for 30 min and collected the unbound fraction (cleaved). The protein was supplemented with 2mM TCEP and 2.5% 1,2-propanediol.</p>

4. CARD domain-/ CTD-/ and loop-truncated His-tagged MDA5

Sample ID	PBC044-C04
Purpose	Crystal trials
Vector	pET28-MHL
AA start to end	306-890
N-terminal tag	MHHHHHHSSGRENLYFQG
C-terminal tag	NA
Expected Mass (Da)	67375/ 65238 after His6 cleavage
Protein sequence	MHHHHHHSSGRENLYFQGLQLRPYQMEVAQPALEGKNIICLPTGSGKTRVAVYIAKDHLDK KKKASEPGKVIVLVNKNVLLVEQLFRKEFQPFLKKWYRVIGLSGDTQLKISFPEVVKSCDIIISTAQI LENSLLNLENGEDAGVQLSDFSLIIDECHHTNKEAVYNNIMRHYLMQKLNKNNRLKKNKPVIP LPQILGLTASPGVGGATKQAKAEHILKLCANLDAFTIKTVKENLDQLKNQIQEPCKKFAIADA TREDPFKEKLEIMTRIQTTCQMSDFGTQPYEQWAIQMEKKAKEGNRKERVCAEHLR KYNEALQINDTIRMIDAYTHLETFYNEEKDKKFAVIEDDLKKPLKLDLDRFLMTLFFENNKML KRLAENPEYENEKLTCLRNTIMEQYTRTEESARGIIFTKTRQSAYALSQWITENEKFAEYGVKA HHLIGAGHSSEFKPMTQNEQKEVSKFRGTGKINLLIATTVAEEGLDIKECNIVIRYGLVTNEIAM VQARGRARADESTYVLVAHSGSGVIERETVNDFREKMMYKAIHCVQNMKPEEYAHKILELQ MQSIMEKKMKTKR

Purified protein (PBC044C04)	
IMAC, TALON (step 1):	<p>From 4L culture, 6 ml beads. W1: hepes 7.4 250mM NaCl 5% glycerol, W2: W1+50 mM Imi, E: W1+250mM Imi Pooled E1-5</p>

SEC (step 2):

Pooled D2-F7 from S200 (33.2 mg)

20241120_MDA5_PBC044C04_S200 001

TEV cleavage (step 3):

Source 30S (step 4):

M f2 f4 f6 f8 f11 g1 g2 g4 g9 g12 h3 h6 a5 a8
P1: f4-g4; S: G5-G8; P2: G9-H4

MDA5_PBC044C04_cut Source S 11212024 001

Intact mass deconvolution (Da):	<p>65242, 67375</p>
Protein yield:	5.2 mg/L culture
Expression and purification protocol	<p>The wild-type gene of MDA5A-S (aa306-644, 663-890) was PCR amplified and subcloned into the pET28-MHL vector. The His6-tagged proteins were expressed in <i>E. coli</i> BL21 (DE3) codon plus RIL strain (Stratagene) with the supplementation of 1 mM isopropyl-1-thio-D-galactopyranoside overnight at 15°C. Harvested cells were resuspended in 20 mM Hepes, pH 7.4, 250 mM NaCl, 5 mM imidazole and 5% glycerol. The cells were lysed chemically with 0.1% CHAPS, 1 mM phenylmethyl sulfonyl fluoride, and benzonase (in-house), followed by sonication at frequency of 8.5 (10" on/10" off) for 2 min (Sonicator 3000, Misoni). The crude extract was clarified by high-speed centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 60 min at 10 °C by Beckman Coulter centrifuge. The clarified lysate was passed through an open column containing equilibrated Ni-NTA resins. The column was washed twice and eluted by 20 mM Hepes pH 7.4, 250 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, containing 5 mM, 50 mM, and 250 mM imidazole, respectively. The eluted protein was supplemented with 2mM TCEP and further purified by size-exclusion chromatography on a Superdex200 26/60 column using an ÄKTA Pure (Cytiva) system with a running buffer containing 20 mM Hepes, pH 7.5, 250 mM NaCl. Proteins were pooled and incubated overnight at 4 °C with tobacco etch virus protease (TEV) to cleave the His6 tag. The protein was further purified by cation exchange chromatography using a Source 30S column pre-equilibrated with 20 mM Hepes, pH 7.4 and eluted with 20 mM Hepes, pH 7.4 at a concentration gradient of 1 M NaCl. The protein was supplemented with 2mM TCEP and 2.5% 1,2-propanediol.</p>

3. Knockdown in iPSC neurons

iPSC cell culture, differentiation, and knockdown protocols

The WTC11 iPSC line [24] and the CVi iPSC line [25] were cultured and differentiated into neurons by the dual SMAD protocol as previously described [26]. Following differentiation, iPSC neurons were passaged to Matrigel-coated 96 well culture plates for shRNA knockdown. iPSC derived neurons were infected with shRNA-containing lentivirus (MOI 5) on Day 2 following neuronal passaging. The cells were cultured with the lentivirus for 72 hours before replacing the media with fresh media. Conditioned medium and cell protein lysates were then harvested for experimental studies following an additional 72 hours. Viral transduction was confirmed by GFP fluorescence. Knockdown efficiency was confirmed by qPCR.

shIFIH1 sequence

ACGAGAGAAGATGATGTATAAA [27].

Cell phenotypic measurements following IFIH1 knockdown

Cells were plated at 250,000 cells/well in a 96 well plate. Media was collected from each well following 72 hours of conditioning to measure secreted A β and cytotoxicity. Protein was harvested according to manufacturer's specifications (Meso Scale Discovery Cat. No. K15121D-2) from corresponding cell lysates for measurements of intracellular Tau. Cytotoxicity was measured by the Promega LDH-Glo Cytotoxicity Assay. A β was measured by the Meso Scale Discovery V-PLEX A β Peptide Panel 1 (6E10) Kit (Cat. No. K15200E-2). Total Tau and pTau (Thre231) were measured by the Meso Scale Discovery Phospho(Thr231)/Total Tau Kit in cell lysates 6 days post transduction (Cat. No. K15121D-2).

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